

(CASE REPORT)

Case study: Ayurvedic approach as an adjuvant therapy in the management of COVID -19

Sachinkumar Sahebrao Patil *, Vijayalaxmi Sujay Patil and Rohit Shivajirao Patil

Department of Kayachikitsa, M.A.M.'s Sumatibhai Shah Ayurved Mahavidyala, Malwadi, Hadapasar, Pune-411028, Maharashtra State, India.

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Abstract

The Corona Virus disease 19 (COVID-19) pandemic is unique and unprecedented in several aspects and has challenged health care systems. In spite of advanced modern medicine still there is no any sure treatment available which cures COVID-19 patient completely. Ayurveda has ability to cure the disease as well as ability to reduce its complication. Material and Method: A 54 years female, medium built patient was admitted in our hospital which is tested COVID-19 RT-PCR positive, having complaints of dry cough, dyspnea on exertion, fever, body ache, Headache on & off, generalized weakness. Treatment was given i.e. *Ayurvedic* as well as modern medicine. Results: Patient started improving from day 4th and at the end of 10th day there was a good improvement in all the symptoms. Discussion: We report this case to show that COVID-19 is a condition where focused *Ayurvedic* treatment, if given, may prevent the deterioration of the disease into a more critical condition. This is also an invaluable opportunity for demonstrating the efficacy of *Ayurveda*.

Keywords: Covid-19; Pandemic; *Ayurveda*; *Janapadhwansa Vikara*

1. Introduction

The whole world is faced with major health crisis following the global pandemic of COVID-19. Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Corona Virus-2 (SARS CoV 2) is a Pandemic disease caused by Novel Corona Virus 2^[1]. This disease is contagious. COVID-19 is a rapidly changing and evolving situation. The overall world population has been facing the aftermath of Pandemic on physical, mental and economic levels. World Health Organization (WHO) is constantly monitoring it and updating the information available regarding its spread, mortality, and morbidity. So far in Modern Western Medicine (MWM), no cure has been found which is specific to COVID-19. From the *Ayurvedic* point of view, COVID-19 is a *Janapadodhwansa Vikara* (epidemic disease). The concept of an epidemic is described in *Charaka Samhita: Vimana Sthana*, Chapter 3^[2]. Factors which are common for all the inhabitants of a country are air, water, location and seasons.^[5] *Janapadodhwansa* isa situation where the environment air, water, land and seasons is vitiated, causing a simultaneous manifestation of a disease among large populations (epidemic) and destroying human habitations.^[3]

COVID-19 is a Novel disease i.e. *Anuktavyadhi* according to *Ayurveda*.^[4] One should not be ashamed of one's inability to name a disease, since all disorders cannot be given standard names. There are innumerable diseases because the same vitiated *Dosha* causes various disorders according to variations in etiology and location.

This article contains case study, where a patient of COVID-19 disease, tested positive with mild to moderate symptoms admitted in our hospital. Managed with *Ayurvedic* along with modern medicine and get fully relieved of his symptoms.

*Corresponding author: Sachinkumar Sahebrao Patil

Department of Kayachikitsa, M.A.M.'s Sumatibhai Shah Ayurved Mahavidyala, Malwadi, Hadapasar, Pune -411028.

As COVID-19 is new disease so a detailed study of the etiology (*Nidana*), status of *Tridosha*, structural elements (*Dushya*) and site of disease (*Sthan*) is discussed in this article.

Aim and Objectives

- To study the Ayurvedic medicines in the management of COVID-19
- To compare the ancient Ayurvedic knowledge with the recent pandemic of COVID-19

2. Case Presentation

2.1. Patient information

A 54 years female, medium built patient was admitted in our hospital, who was tested COVID -19 RT-PCR positive.

2.2. Symptoms

Jwar on and off since 2-3 days

Alpa Shushka Kasa since 2 days

Ayaseen Shwaskashthata since 2-3 days

Dourbalya, Agnimandya since 7-8 days

2.3. Samanyaparikshana

- Pulse – 98/min; *Nadi – Vataj*
- B.P. – 140/70 mm of Hg; *Mala - Asamyaka*
- RS – B/L basal crepts; *Mutra - Samyaka*
- CVS – S1S2 normal; *Jivha - Saama*
- CNS – Conscious oriented; *Kshudha – Mandya*
- P/A – Soft; *Shabda –aspastha*
- RR – 30/min; *Sparsha - Ushna*
- SPO2 – 94 % @ R.A; *Druka – Prakruta*
- Temp. – 93.2^o F; *Aakruti - Madhyama*

Details of the symptoms, number of days it lasted, tests performed and medicines recommended are given below in Table.

2.4. Past Medical History

Patient was known case of Diabetes mellitus and Hypertension along with Ischemic heart disease since 10-12 years and on regular medications.

2.5. Diagnosis

Diagnosis was made on the basis of symptoms, season and RT-PCR COVID-19 test.^[5]

CXR (P/A) view

2.6. Ayurvedic interpretation of the patient condition

2.6.1. Samprapti Ghatak

- *Dosha - Kapha - Vaata – Pitta*
- *Dushya - Rasadidhatu*
- *Vyadhiswabhav - Ashukari*
- *Srotas - Rasavaha, Pranavaha, Annavaha*
- *Vikarprakruti – Darun*

- *Udbhavsthan - Nasa Pradesh*
- *Utpattisthan - Rasavaha, Annavaaha, Sarvdeha*
- *Agni – Vishamagni*

2.6.2. HETU

Pradnyaparadha+ Janapadodhwansa + Aoupsargika Vyadhi

Pradnyaparadha [6]

Contravening the rules & regulation of – lockdown, social distancing, travelling, staying at home, and use of Mask.

Janapadodhwansa

Factors which are familiar to the people under a particular community like air (*Vayu*), water (*Jala*), region (*Desha*), seasons (*Kala*), sinful acts (*Adharma*) in the form of war are responsible for *Janapadodhwansa*.

Aoupsargika Vyadhi [7]

According to the *Sushrut Samhita*, expired air or inhalation of a droplet from an infected person (*Nishvasat*), eating in the same plate with others (*Sahabhojanat*), sharing beds (*Sahashayyanat*), using clothes, garlands & utensils used by an infected person (*Vastramalyanulepanat*) can be considered as the mode of transmission of COVID-19 pandemics.

Purvaroop

Agnimandya, Angamarda, Mandjwara

Roop

Increased *Agnimandya, Angamard, Jwara, Shwas, Kasa*

2.6.3. Samprapti

Figure 1 Samprapti of Disease**2.7. Treatment given****Table 1** Assessment & Treatment Protocol

Day	Symptoms	Treatment
Day 1	Dry cough Dyspnea on exertion Fever on and off Body ache Headache on & off Generalized weakness	<i>Aayushkwath Vati 2 BD</i> <i>Sukshmatriphala Vati 2 TDS</i> <i>Sanshamani Vati 2 TDS</i> <i>Dhatrinisha Vati 2BD</i> <i>Vishan Yoga (Rasasindoor 125 mg+Shrungra Bhasma250mg+Pooshkarmool 500 mg + SitopaladiChurna 1 gm = 1 TSF TDS with koshnajala)</i> <i>Twakadi Dhoopan TDS</i> <i>Hemgharbh Pottali Rasyan Chatan with Adrakswaras QID</i> <i>Haridralavanjala Kaval TDS</i> Inj. MPS 40mg IV stat Inj. H. Actrapid Insulin according to BSL Tab. Azee 500 1 OD Tab. Telma-AM (40+5) 1OD Tab. Glycomate SR 500mg 1BD Tab. Vit C 1 OD Tab. Supradyn 1 OD Cap. Ecosprin AV 150/20 1HS
Day2	Dry cough Dyspnea on exertion Fever on and off Body ache Headache ↓ Generalized weakness	<i>Aayushkwath Vati 2 BD</i> <i>Sukshmatriphala Vati 2 TDS</i> <i>Sanshamani Vati 2 TDS</i> <i>Dhatrinisha Vati 2BD</i> <i>Vishan Yoga (Rasasindoor 125 mg + Shrungra Bhasm250mg + Pooshkarmool 500 mg + SitopaladiChurna 1 gm) = 1 TSF TDS with KoshnaJala</i> <i>Twakadi Dhoopan TDS</i> <i>Hemgharbh Pottali Rasayan Chatan with AdrakSwaras QID</i> <i>Haridralavanjala Kaval TDS</i> Inj. Dexa 4 mg IV BD Inj. H. Actrapid Insulin according to BSL Tab. Azee 500 1 OD Tab. Telma-AM (40+5) 1OD Tab. Glycomate SR 500 BD Tab. Vitamin C 1 OD Tab. Supradyn 1 OD Cap. Ecosprin AV 150/20 1HS
Day 3	Mild dry cough Dyspnea on exertion Mild fever ↓ Body ache ↓	Same medicine continued

	Headache Generalized weakness↓	
Day 4	Dry cough ↓ ↓ Dyspnea on exertion Fever ↓ Body ache ↓ Headache ↓ Generalized weakness	Same medicine continued
Day 5	Dyspnea ↓ Fever } Body ache } Weakness } 25-30% Headache }	<i>Aayushkwath Vati 2 BD</i> <i>Sukshmatriphala Vati 2 TDS</i> <i>Sanshamani Vati 2 TDS</i> <i>Dhatrinisha Vati 2BD</i> <i>Vishan Yoga (Rasasindoor 125 mg + ShrunghaBhasma 250 mg + Pooshkarmool 500 mg+SitopaladiChurna 1gm) = TDS with Koshnajala</i> <i>TwakadiDhoopan TDS</i> <i>Hemgarbha Pottali Rasayan Chatan with AdrakSwaras QID</i> <i>Haridralavanjala Kaval TDS</i> Inj. H. Actrapid Insulin according to BSL Tab. Azee 500 1 OD Tab. Telma AM (40+5)10D Tab. Glycomate SR 500 1BD Tab. Vitamin C 1 OD Tab. Supradyn 1 OD Cap. Ecosprin AV 150/20 1HS
Day 6	30-40 % relief in all below symptoms - Dry cough Dyspnea on exertion Fever Body ache Headache Generalized weakness	Same medicine continued
Day 7	40-50% relief in all symptoms.	<i>Aayushkwath Vati 2 BD</i> <i>Sukshmatriphala Vati 2 TDS</i> <i>Sanshamani Vati 2 TDS</i> <i>Dhatrinisha Vati 2 BD</i> <i>Vishan Yoga (Rasasindoor 125 mg + ShrunghaBhasma 250 mg + Pooshkarmool 500 mg + Sitopaladi Churna1 gm)= 1 TSF TDS with koshnajala</i> <i>Twakadi Dhoopan TDS</i> <i>Haridralavanjala Kaval</i> Tab.Telma–AM (40+5) 10D Tab. Glycomate SR 500mg BD Tab. Vit C 1 OD

		Tab. Supradyn 1 OD Cap. Ecosprin AV 150/20 1HS
Day 8	50-60 % relief in all symptoms.	Same medicine continued
Day 9	50-60 % relief in all symptoms.	Same medicine continued
Day 10	60-70 % relief in all symptoms.	Same medicine continued

2.8. Details of Ayurvedic Management

2.8.1. Aayushkwath Vati ^[8]

Table 2 Drug Content & Mode of Action of Aayushkwath Vati

Name	Latin name	Doshghnata	Mode of action
<i>Tulasi</i>	<i>Ocimum sanctum</i> (Linn.)	<i>Kapha – Vatahara</i>	<i>Vishamajwarahara, Shwaasa-Kasaghna, Bhutaghni</i>
<i>Shunthi</i>	<i>Zinzeberofficinale</i> (Roxb.)	<i>Kapha – Vatahara</i>	<i>Deepan, Pachana, Jwarahara</i>
<i>Krishna Marich</i>	<i>Piper longum</i> (Linn.)	<i>Kapha – Vatahara</i>	<i>KasaShwasahara, Rasayan</i>
<i>Dalchini</i>	<i>Cinnamomum zeylanicum</i> (Breyn.)	<i>Kapha – Vatahara</i>	<i>Deepan, Pachan, Vataanulomana, Ojovardhak</i>

2.8.2. Sukshma TriphalaVati

Table 3 Drug Content & Mode of Action of Sukshma TriphalaVati

<i>Amalaki</i>	<i>Embilica officinalis</i> (Gaertn.)	<i>Tridosahara</i>	<i>Rasayan, Vibandhahar, Pramehaghna</i>
<i>Haritaki</i>	<i>Terminalia chebula</i> (Retz.)	<i>Tridosahara</i>	<i>Rasayan, Malashodhak, Pramehaghna, Kasaghna</i>
<i>Bibhitaki</i>	<i>Terminalia bellerica</i> (Roxb.)	<i>Kaphaghna</i>	<i>Bhedan, Kasaghna, Krimighna, Swarbhedahar</i>
<i>Guduchi</i>	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i> (Willd.)	<i>Tridosahara</i>	<i>Rasayan, Jwaraghna, Hrudyā, Krimihara, Shwas-Kasahara</i>
<i>Haridra</i>	<i>Curcuma longa</i> (Linn.)	<i>Kaphapittahara</i>	<i>Shothaghna, Kasaghna, Mehahara,</i>
<i>Kajjali</i>	<i>Black Sulphide Of Mercury</i>	<i>Tridosahara</i>	<i>Jantughna, Saptadhatuwardhan,</i>

2.8.3. Samshamani Vati^[9]

Table 4 Drug Content & Mode of Action of Samshamani Vati

<i>Guduchi</i>	<i>Tinosporacordifolia</i>	<i>Tridosahara</i>	<i>Rasayan, Jwaraghna, Hrudyā, Krimihara, Shwas-Kasahara</i>
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	(Willd.)		
Kajjali	Black Sulphide of Mercury		Jantughna, Saptadhatuwardhan,

2.8.4. Dhatrinisha Vati

Table 5 Drug Content & Mode of Action of Dhatrinisha Vati

Amalaki	<i>Emblicoefficialis</i> (Gaertn.)	Tridosahara	Rasayan,vibandhahar, Pramehaghna
Haridra	<i>Curcuma longa</i> (Linn.)	Kaphapittahara	Shothaghna, Kasaghna,Mehahara,

2.8.5. Vishan Yoga

Table 6 Drug Content & Mode of Action of Vishan Yoga

Drugs	Doshghnata	Drug ation
<i>Rasasindura</i> ^[10] (<i>Shuddhaparad, Shuddhagandhak, Shuddhanavasagar</i>)	Balances Vata, Pitta, Kapha Kaphahara	Rasayan, Shothahara, Shwasa - Kasahar , Shwasanakjwarahara
<i>Shrungabhasama</i> ^[11] (<i>Mrugashruna</i>)	Tridosahara	Hrudya, Kaphajashwashara, Shwasanakjwarahara, act on Pranavahsrotasa
<i>Pusharamool</i> ^[12] (<i>Inularacemoso</i>)	Vataghna	Vatakapha-Jwarahara, Shothaghna, Shwasa- Kasahara,
<i>Sitopaladichoorna</i> ^[13] (<i>Sitopala, Pippali,Ela,Twaka</i>)	Tridosahara	Shwaskasaghna, Kanthya, Swarya, Agnivardhaka,Aruchinashaka

2.8.6. Hemgharbh Pottali Rasayan

Table 7: Drug Content & Mode of Action of Hemgharbh Pottali Rasayan

Drugs	Latin name	Doshghnata	Drug Action
<i>Shuddha Parada</i>	Purified mercury	Tridosahara	Sukshmasrotas,Yogavahi
<i>Shuddha Gandhak</i>	Purified sulphur	VataPittashamak	Veeryakara, Pushtikara, Drudhadaha,Vahnikara, Prajakara
<i>Swarna Bhasma</i>	Gold bhasma	Tridosahara	Ayurkaram, Rasayan, Prabhakaram, AkhilaVyadhiVidhwansi, Bhutaveshaprashanti, Pushti-Prakashi
<i>Tamra Bhasma</i>	Copper bhasma	Pitta kaphashamak	Rasayan, Balya
<i>Kumari Swaras</i>	Aloe verajuice extract	Vatt Pitta Shamak	Bhedeni ,Rasayan,Bhruhan,Jawarhar

2.9. Twakadi Dhoopan

2.9.1. Ingredients

Twaka, Ela,Tamalpatra, Vala, Chandan, Nagakeshara, Renukbeeja, Agaru Padmakashtha,Musta.

Use - main action and properties of Dhoopan Dravyas are antimicrobial, antiviral, antifungal. Fumigation with the help of these drugs destroys worms and germs in environment.^[14]

3. Discussion

3.1. Limitations

Since this is a single case study, it calls for a larger sample to be studied, before we can develop a standard protocol for the treatment of COVID-19. The physical distance between the patient and doctor made it difficult to examine and observe the patient directly. There are a large number of Ayurvedic medicines that are currently in use for all types of *Vata-Kaphaja* and *Sannipatajwara* which may prove to be effective for COVID-19.

3.2. Strengths

It is noticed that the patient's condition did not deteriorate. So it can be presumed that the management of COVID-19 with the given *Ayurvedic* medicines arrested the progress of the disease to a more serious state. Despite the patient having cough and fever, the patient did not worsen and develop severe breathlessness. This patient had recovered in 10 days. Hence it can be said that the duration of the disease was presumably shorter because of the *Ayurvedic* medicines.

Figure 2 Chest X-ray Assessment during Treatment

The regulated diet played an important supportive role in the cure. The diet was advised so that it did not further aggravate the *Doshas*, it was easy to digest (*Laghu*), it stimulated the digestive fire (*Agni Deepanam*) and it nourished the patient. The diet recommended for the patient, namely soup made of moong dal and cooked parboiled rice is included in the recommended diet in management of fevers. These are two of several preparations as described in the texts, as part of a larger detailing of food preparations and their effects on *Doshas* and diseases. We report this case to show that COVID-19 is a condition where usage of *Ayurvedic* medicines & diet might have contributed to the case not turning critically ill.

Rsayan Chikitsa is recommended for treatment of *Janapadoshwamsa*. It helps to maintain systemic and local immunity (*Vyadhikshamatva*) of an individual. *Vyadhikshamatva* of an individual is directly proportional to strength of that individual. Strength is *Bala* which is *Dehabala* (Body strength), *Agnibala* (Digestive capacity) and *Manobala* (Mental strength).^[15]

Hereby showing the chest x-ray of patient admitted taken on day 1st, day 5th and day 10th respectively numbered 1, 2 and 3.

- Chest x-ray suggestive of bilateral lower lobe haziness. On auscultation, patient had bilateral lower lobe crepts, mild exertional dyspnoea, with cough and fever.
- Chest x-ray suggestive of increased bilateral lower lobe haziness. On auscultation, patient had bilateral lower lobe crepts, mild exertional dyspnoea, with cough and fever. Patient was stable and didn't deteriorate.

Chest x-ray suggestive of decreased bilateral lower lobe haziness. All symptoms including exertional dyspnoea, cough and fever were decreased. On auscultation, breathing sounds were clear.

4. Conclusion

We report this case to show that COVID-19 is a condition where focused Ayurvedic treatment, if given, may prevent the deterioration of the disease into a more critical condition. This patient's presentation was not mild. But he didn't become critically ill owing to Ayurvedic intervention and regulated diet. India is in a position to use the wealth of knowledge available in the Indian Systems of Medicine, to cure this disease and control the epidemic. This is also an invaluable opportunity for demonstrating the efficacy of Ayurveda.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that there was no conflict of interest regarding the publication of manuscript.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from the individual participant included in the study.

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Author's short Biography

Dr. Sachinkumar Sahebrao Patil, M.D. (Kayachikitsa) Medicine, Ph.D. (Kayachikitsa) Medicine, M.B.A. (H.R.), P.G.D.E.M.S., D.Y.A. Professor and H.O.D., Ph.D. Guide, M.D. Guide, Department of Kayachikitsa, M.A.M.'s Sumatibhai Shah Ayurved Mahavidyala, Malwadi, Hadapsar, Pune - 411028, Maharashtra State, India. He is working as Ayurved Physician, Panchakarma Specialist since last 17 Years. He is a Board of Studies Member for Paraclinical Ayurved Board of Maharashtra University of Health Sciences Nashik. He is a Faculty member for Post Graduate Paraclinical Ayurved Board of Maharashtra University of Health Sciences, Nashik. He is working as a Research Faculty for Research Methodology and Medical Statistics of Maharashtra University of Health Sciences, Nashik. He is a Ph.D. supervisor for five Ph.D. Kayachikitsa (Medicine) students and M.D. GUIDE for 27 M.D. Kayachikitsa (Medicine) students out of which 18 M.D. Kayachikitsa (Medicine) students. His research experience is 14 Years. His research interest in Anxiety Disorder, Diabetes Mellitus, Obesity, Hyperacidity, Diarrhoea, Anaemia etc.